

USE OF SOLAR ENERGY

Timirov X.N.

Buxoro muhandislik texnologiya instituti

Annotatsiya: In the thesis, studies were conducted on increasing the quality of economic efficiency, reducing its cost, and increasing labor productivity by using natural electricity in buildings using direct solar energy.

Key words: energy, sun, earth, oil, natural gas.

Economical use of fuel sources has led to the widespread use of wind energy, a continuously renewable source of energy, to reduce the cost of mechanical energy and, consequently, electricity. Currently, the energy system of Uzbekistan provides energy to 19,000 industrial, 80,000 agricultural, 19,000 communal and 3.5 million household consumers. Every year, the sun's rays bring a huge amount of energy to the earth, i.e. energy equal to $62 \cdot 10^{16}$ kWh. 60% of this energy is spent on heating the earth's atmosphere, 25.5% on the ocean and sea, and 14.5% on the land. Of this, 2.5 percent is converted into mechanical energy of wind, 0.14 percent into mechanical energy of river movement, 0.12 percent into chemical energy of various fuels, wood, peat, coal, oil, and burning shale. If we take into account that the surface of the cross section of the earth is $127.6 \cdot 10^6$ km², the energy of sunlight falling on the earth is $176.6 \cdot 10^{12}$ kW, which means that in one year the earth receives $1.56 \cdot 10^{18}$ kWh ($1.6 \cdot 10^{18}$ kWh of sunlight energy decreases.

STEP CONFERENCE

The golden rays of the sun bring to our earth 150,000 billion kWh of wind energy and 33,000 billion kWh of water energy per year. In forests, 220,000 billion kilowatt hours of energy are collected annually due to sunlight. In addition, thanks to solar energy, huge energy reserves have been accumulated in the earth's crust for thousands of years. For example, there are 3,580,000 billion kWh of energy in coal, 480,000 billion kWh in peat, 700,000 billion kWh in combustible shale, and 80,000 billion kWh in natural gas. Currently, mankind uses less than one thousandth of these huge reserves per year. Today, it is known that the sun is like a giant nuclear reactor, where nuclear reactions take place at high pressure and temperature. Due to this reaction, in the process of turning hydrogen into a helium nucleus, the temperature in the active zone of the solar reactor exceeds 10 million degrees. This reaction in the sun produces 560 million tons of helium per second and turns 4 million tons of hydrogen into energy. They tried to use solar energy in the distant past. The ancient Greek scientist Archimedes recorded in history that he burned the ships of the Romans by shining the sun's rays through a system of mirrors. Solar energy is widely used in foreign countries. A solar power plant was built under the leadership of physicist-chemist Felix Tremba in Odeysde, Northern France, with a capacity of 1100 kW and a temperature of 3800 degrees. In 1816, Icelander Robert Stirling created a solar engine using a helio-device. In 1954,

STEP CONFERENCE

American Ges Repot and Bruce Kaymike suggested the convenience of an airplane for direct use of sunlight. 20 years later, researchers from the London College proved the correctness of this idea. New designs and projects of solar panels and concentrators were presented. Research conducted by scientists in Russia, USA, France, England, Australia, Argentina, Netherlands, India, Germany, Israel, Canada, Italy, Japan and many other developed countries on the use of non-conventional energy sources has good results

is giving For example, in Germany, Israel, and the USA, 30-35 percent of houses are heated in winter and cooled in summer using solar energy.

List of main textbooks and study guides used

Mirziyoyev SH. —2017-2021 yillarda qayta tiklanuvchi energetikani yanada rivojlantirish, iqtisodiyot tarmoqlari va ijtimoiy sohada energiya samaradorligini oshirish chora-tadbirlari dasturi togrisidagi 26.05.2017 y., PQ-3012-son Qarori.

2. Yuldoshev I.A., Saitov E.B. Quyosh panellarini o'rnatish, sozlash va ishlatish. Oquv qo'llanma. –Toshkent: Noshir nashriyoti, 2017.

Electronic resources

1. <http://alternativenergy.ru>

2. <http://www.energy-bio.ru>

3. www.viecosolar.com